

Paper	Title	Doi
1	Electronic Health Record Usability: Associations with Nurse and Patient Outcomes in Hospitals	doi:10.1097/MLR.0000000000001536
2	The Influence of Electronic Health Record Use on Physician Burnout: Cross-Sectional Survey	doi: 10.2196/19274
3	Documentation dynamics: Note composition, burden, and physician efficiency	DOI: 10.1111/1475-6773.14097
4	Electronic Health Record Use and Perceptions among Urologic Surgeons	DOI https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0043-1763513
5	Electronic Health Record Usability, Satisfaction, and Burnout for Family Physicians	doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.26956
6	<i>Electronic Health Records and the Disappearing Patient</i>	DOI: 10.1111/maq.12375
7	The Adoption of the Electronic Health Record by Physicians	DOI https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0039-1695006
8	Care integration within and outside health system boundaries	DOI: 10.1111/1475-6773.13578
9	Surgeon Burnout and Usage of Personal Communication Devices: Examining the Technology “Empowerment/Enslavement Paradox”	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2022.12.023
10	Physician stress and burnout: the impact of health information technology	doi: 10.1093/jamia/ocy145
11	Associations of physician burnout with organizational electronic health record support and after-hours charting	doi: 10.1093/jamia/ocab053
12	The Effect of Electronic Health Record Burden on Pediatricians’ Work–Life Balance and Career Satisfaction	DOI https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0041-1732402
13	Focus Section on Health IT Usability: Perceived Burden of EHRs on Physicians at Different Stages of Their Career	DOI https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0038-1648222
14	Association of Electronic Health Record Design and Use Factors With Clinician Stress and Burnout	doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2019.9609
15	Electronic medical records and physician stress in primary care: results from the MEMO Study	doi:10.1136/amiajnl-2013-001875
16	The implementation of a multidisciplinary, electronic health record embedded care pathway to improve structured data recording and decrease	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2024.105344

	electronic health record burden	
17	Resource Utilization Among Portal Users Who Send Messages: A Retrospective Cohort Study	Michelle Bryan, MD;
18	Developing and Evaluating Large Language Model-Generated Emergency Medicine Handoff Notes	doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.48723 (Reprinted)
19	Ambient virtual scribes: Mutuo Health's AutoScribe as a case study of artificial intelligence-based technology	DOI: 10.1177/0840470419872775
20	Psychiatric Emergency Services - Can Duty-Hour Changes Help Residents and Patients?	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11126-018-9579-2
21	Machine Learning Methods for Identifying Critical Data Elements in Nursing Documentation	DOI: 10.1097/NNR.0000000000000315
22	The State of Oncology Practice in America, 2018: Results of the ASCO Practice Census Survey	DOI: https://doi.org/10.1200/JOP.18.00149
23	Exploring critical factors influencing physicians' acceptance of mobile electronic medical records based on the dual-factor model: a validation in Taiwan	DOI 10.1186/s12911-014-0125-3
24	Barriers to Adoption of a Child-Abuse Clinical Decision Support System in Emergency Departments	DOI 10.5811/westjem.18501
25	Emergency Medicine Residents on Electronic Medical Records: Perspectives and Advice	DOI: 10.7759/cureus.4027
26	Quantifying and Visualizing Nursing Flowsheet Documentation Burden in Acute and Critical Care	Sarah Collins RN, PhD1,2
27	Understanding the Association Between Electronic Health Record Satisfaction and the Well-Being of Nurses: Survey Study	doi: 10.2196/13996
28	Classification and analysis of asynchronous communication content between care team members involved in breast cancer treatment	doi: 10.1093/jamiaopen/ooab049
29	Variation in Family Physicians' Experiences Across Different Electronic Health Record Platforms: a Descriptive Study	DOI: 10.1007/s11606-023-08169-5
30	Evaluating the Impact of a Point-of-Care Cardiometabolic Clinical	doi: 10.2196/38385

	Decision Support Tool on Clinical Efficiency Using Electronic Health Record Audit Log Data: Algorithm Development and Validation	
31	The association between use of ambient voice technology documentation during primary care patient encounters, documentation burden, and provider burnout	https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/cmab092
32	Enhancing clinical documentation with ambient artificial intelligence: a quality improvement survey assessing clinician perspectives on work burden, burnout, and job satisfaction	https://doi.org/10.1093/jamiaopen/ooaf013
33	Inter-Specialty Communication for Older and High-Risk Surgical Patients: “A Huge Opportunity to Really Impact Our Patients’ Care”	DOI: 10.1177/07334648241302458
34	Saving Time for Patient Care by Optimizing Physician Note Templates: A Pilot Study	doi: 10.3389/fdgth.2021.772356
35	<i>Physician Stress During Electronic Health Record Inbox Work: In Situ Measurement With Wearable Sensors</i>	doi: 10.2196/24014
36	<i>Burnout Among United States Orthopaedic Surgery Residents</i>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsurg.2020.02.019
37	Differences in Total and After-hours Electronic Health Record Time Across Ambulatory Specialties	doi: 10.1001/jamainternmed.2021.0256
38	Factors That Influence Clinician Experience with Electronic Health Records	Vimal Mishra